

Recommended citation: Cory, C. Z., Sucala, V. I., & Carroll, S. (2019). The development of a Gold Standard Project Based Learning (GSPBL) engineering curriculum to improve Entrepreneurial Competence for success in the 4th industrial revolution. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 280-291). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656196.

The development of a Gold Standard Project Based Learning (GSPBL) engineering curriculum to improve Entrepreneurial Competence for success in the 4th industrial revolution

CZ Cory¹

Senior Lecturer in Engineering & Entrepreneurship
University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom
Email: c.cory@exeter.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4708-9025>

VI Sucala

Senior Lecturer in Engineering & Entrepreneurship
University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom
Email: i.sucala@exeter.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3071-5691>

S Carroll

Senior Lecturer in Structural Engineering
University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom
Email: s.p.carroll@exeter.ac.uk

¹ Corresponding Author CZ Cory c.cory@exeter.ac.uk

Conference Key Areas: 4th Industrial Revolution, Lifelong learning.

Keywords: Project Based Learning, Entrepreneurship, 21st Century Skills, 4th Industrial Revolution, Industry Collaboration.

ABSTRACT

An engineering graduate in the 4th industrial revolution must learn how to learn and unlearn, to keep up to date with rapidly changing technology and apply entrepreneurial competence to solve complex problems [1].

A pilot module facilitated action research with a methodology that combined Gold Standard Project Based Learning (GSPBL) [2] and EntreComp [3] as part of strategic curriculum development. The authentic industry-linked module began with an interactive launch that provided students with access to Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) and Virtual Reality (VR) equipment and lectures on Building Information Modelling (BIM) and entrepreneurship. Initial student feedback was positive and included ‘*you can already sense that the group projects are really going to help us collaborate and also learn about LiDAR*’ and ‘*the transferrable skills are really useful for future projects and employment*’.

The driving question was ‘*How can you apply LiDAR scanning technology to create a new product, service or process?*’. PBL teams were encouraged to investigate LiDAR scanning technology to uncover and assess business opportunities using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) [4]. Students were incredibly creative, engaged and highly motivated during the mid-way storyboard checkpoint with cross-disciplinary academic and peer critique and revision. Student voice and choice is a major aspect of GSPBL

and students thrive on the independence and flexibility of the GSPBL structure that culminates in a *public product* short video pitch summative assessment.

The combination of GSPBL and EntreComp form a valuable methodology to develop the competence required for success as a professional and entrepreneurial engineer during the 4th industrial revolution.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the development of a pilot module, Entrepreneurship 1, in the 1st year of all engineering degree programmes at the University of Exeter. The pilot module tested the proposed methodology on a small scale with 1 module completed in 2018/2019 before a second module, Entrepreneurship 2, is introduced in 2019/2020. These new modules will not only test the proposed methodology but also start to build a new culture of teaching and learning with both staff and students. The authors are currently updating all engineering degree programmes with a focus on GSPBL and entrepreneurship. The lessons learned from introducing the new methodology as part of the pilot module will influence the design and delivery of the new engineering degree programmes in 2020/2021.

The integrated strategy advised by QAA in 2012 ‘to help students develop and demonstrate entrepreneurial effectiveness’ [5, pg. 24] includes a move towards teaching, learning and assessment that covers emerging situations, innovation, active learning, subjective experience, multimedia communication, authentic activities, learning from failure, self-reliance and resilience [5].

More recent higher education guidelines (2018) for enterprise and entrepreneurship education are summarised below in *Table 1* [6].

Table 1. Selected points of focus from QAA delivery methods and assessment [6].

Delivery Methods	Assessment
Contextualised approach	Reflection on entrepreneurial activities
Identify and solve problems	Teamwork and peer review
Enhance entrepreneurial capabilities	Realisation of failure through reflection can inform positive assessment
Action based practical activities	Assessment with pitches and business modelling are effective
Cross-disciplinary approaches	External experts are useful for inspiration
High engagement activities such as simulations for experiential learning	Portfolio style of collated work to demonstrate progression
Guest specialists and entrepreneurs	
Reflection to consolidate learning points and plan for future action	
Illustrate impact on employability as well as entrepreneurship	

There are a growing number of innovative educational establishments moving towards experiential, active learning methodologies [7, 8]. The future focus of Universities should be on complex challenges, peer-to-peer learning and lecturers as facilitators [9].

GSPBL has been developed over the last 20 years by the Buck Institute for Education (BIE) [10]. BIE have recently rebranded as PBL Works and projects are designed with 7 essential elements [2] and 21st century skills are developed during GSPBL projects including communication, collaboration, adaptability, critical thinking, problem solving, technological literacy, creative thinking and self-management [11]. PBL Works are a non-profit educational organisation with a well-established and trusted track record in GSPBL. They are part of the steering committee committed to High Quality PBL [12] with partners that include Google and High-Tech High Graduate School. They provide a range of training courses from introduction to coaching and hold an annual international PBL Works conference.

EntreComp was developed by the European Commission to create a standard framework for entrepreneurship as a competence [3]. It 'identifies the competences that make someone entrepreneurial. These can then be used to support entrepreneurial learning in different settings ...' [3, pg. 13]. EntreComp complements GSPBL as the progression model [3, pg. 20] can be used to guide entrepreneurial competences from the 1st year module (foundation) to the 2nd year module (intermediate).

The authors suggest that the combination of GSPBL [2] and EntreComp [3] create a methodology that could effectively plan, deliver and assess appropriate modules within the new engineering programme.

This style of learning and teaching requires not just a change in degree programmes but also a change in students' mindset away from individual study towards the building of a learning community that encourages collaboration. Academics also have to adjust to new teaching styles to fully build the culture. Singapore University of Technology and Design (SUTD) is a 'recently-established engineering and architecture specialist university that offers a design-centred, multidisciplinary and project-based curriculum ...'. Students and faculty members comment that there is a feeling of camaraderie and community spirit with 'a flat hierarchy and a start-up atmosphere'.

Changes towards a project-based curriculum can be met with initial resistance from students and staff who may find the transition from the current traditional teaching and learning challenging [7]. Thus, the rationale for this study was to utilise a new module, Entrepreneurship 1, as a pilot for the proposed teaching and learning methodology.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Essential Project Based Elements

The design of GSPBL projects is an iterative process and requires regular collaboration, reflection and flexibility between the teaching team to ensure the highest quality projects are designed. Whilst undergoing the project design process, the authors continuously referred to the 7 essential project design elements [2] to ensure the project adhered to the required HQ PBL [12]. The 7 essential project design elements are shown in *Fig. 1* as these are interconnected throughout the project design steps described in section 2.2.

Fig. 1. Gold Standard PBL – Seven Essential Project Design Elements [2].

2.2 Designing the project

The methodology for designing this pilot module followed the ‘5 steps for designing a project’ [13] for GSPBL.

2.2.1 Develop and idea and connect it to standards and other learning goals

Project ideas can be developed alongside competitions created by professional associations, through co-created briefs with students, community projects or global issues. The aim for this project was to create an open-ended *challenging problem or question* (Fig. 1) to facilitate the exploration of technology related to the 4th industrial revolution. The authors had previous industry experience and links in Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) and a new Virtual Reality (VR) suite had recently been commissioned within the engineering department.

The driving question was:

‘How can you apply LiDAR scanning technology to create a new product, service or process?’

The driving question prompted students to find an application for the technology inside the LiDAR scanner, which widened the scope for discovery and exploration. This aligns with the foundation level in the EntreComp progression model [3].

The authors aligned the project with the requirements for the Accreditation of Higher Education Programmes (AHEP) in engineering [14] and the EntreComp framework [3] to ensure both technical and entrepreneurship learning objectives were met. The EntreComp wheel (Fig. 2) illustrates 3 competence areas and 15 competences and

'can be used as a guide when designing a new activity and/or a model for you to use or adapt for learning and assessment' [3, pg. 13].

Fig. 2. The EntreComp wheel: 3 competence areas and 15 competences [3, pg. 14].

2.2.2 Decide what major products or performances students will create and how they will be made public

This step of the project design process included many parts of the 7 essential project design elements (Fig. 1). A formative assessment for *critique & revision*, allowed students time for *reflection* and provided two opportunities for the team to present their *public product*. *Student voice & choice* was facilitated as part of both major products and they provided opportunity for student to work towards many of the 5 competences of the EntreComp wheel under the *ideas & opportunities* competence area.

The *first major product* was a storyboard to plan out each team's final video pitch using established storyboarding techniques. This was made public through students presenting their work to Lectures in Engineering and Entrepreneurship, academic colleagues from the Business School and colleagues from Business Support. The cross-discipline formative feedback session created an exciting atmosphere with *authenticity* where students were discussing their business ideas directly with staff who had both technical and entrepreneurship experience. Feedback was provided verbally and via a highlighted formative assessment sheet to provide teams with clear critique for revision before the final summative assessment. Peer feedback was facilitated through a gallery walk where post it notes were attached to the storyboards with constructive comments related to the categories detailed in the formative assessment sheet.

The *second major product* was a 2.5-minute video pitch for the team's final product, service or process and facilitated the requirement to work towards many of the EntreComp competences. This was made public through students introducing their video, playing the video and justifying their work through a Q&A with a panel of judges.

Other teams in the allocated sessions viewed at least 8 other team presentations in their session thus expanding their knowledge of LiDAR technology and potential applications through formal peer learning.

2.2.3 Map out the steps in the project and create a timeline

This step of the project design included *sustained inquiry* and *student voice and choice* parts of the essential project design elements (Fig. 1).

Students were provided with an introductory lecture and deadlines for the two major products. Guidance was given to help teams to plan, agree and manage tasks using project plans, project logs and individual work packages. Teams were encouraged to follow the Stage Gate Innovation Process [15] and during Stage 2 'Build a Business Case' they made use of the business model canvas [4]. Further guidance was provided via videos, examples and templates on a VLE to facilitate blended learning.

This method follows the guidelines for HQ PBL suggesting that students need to think about what is required to complete a project and take 'an active role in planning and carrying out project activities' [12, pg. 8] and be given the 'opportunity to learn the tools and methods of project management' [12, pg. 8].

Three weeks after the completion of the second major project, teams were asked to download and complete a reflective report template to facilitate reflection on their technical skills and entrepreneurial competences, challenges faced, attempts to overcome challenges and appreciation of peer learning. Teams were also prompted to consider the impact this module had on their future ability to spot opportunities and create value for their company either as an entrepreneur or an intrapreneur. Finally, students set themselves targets for the 2nd year Entrepreneurship 2 module.

2.2.4 Plan activities and workshops and gather resources

Innovation workshops were provided by alumni entrepreneurs to inspire and motivate students by offering practical advice on how students could learn from their innovation journeys. A range of alumni attended to provide best practice examples of innovation during start-up, in a micro enterprise, in a social enterprise and within an established company.

Other practical activities included Technical Skills Workshops (TSWs) in 3D modelling, 3D printing, machine tools and electronics to equip students with specialised knowledge and skills for direct application to the main project. For example, the 3D modelling task was to model a LiDAR scanner head and during the machine tools workshop students created a plumb bob used to set up LiDAR scanners over fixed marker points. The practical electronics TSWs demonstrated aspects of the technology inside LiDAR equipment using a mini LiDAR scanner to demonstrate the control of key actions within the LiDAR scanner.

2.2.5 Plan an engaging launch for the project

This step of the project design process aimed to introduce the *challenging problem or question* and fulfil the *authenticity* part of the essential project design elements (Fig. 1).

The project was launched with presentations from a LiDAR scanning operator, an entrepreneur with several technology focussed companies (Teradata UK Ltd, BIM

Surveys Ltd, Snow-Forecast.com Ltd) and a Partner leading Building Information Modelling (BIM) in an engineering consultancy (Hoare Lea LLP). The LiDAR scanning operator explained the technical details of the technology inside LiDAR scanners and how short-range and long-range LiDAR scanners functioned. This created a foundation of knowledge to introduce the driving question defined in 2.2.1. The entrepreneur enthused students with his personal entrepreneurship journey and provided further details on BIM. The Partner at Hoare Lea presented BIM case studies from international projects and highlighted the importance of digital engineering to facilitate global collaboration.

The engagement with industry experts continued with LiDAR scanning demonstrations where students were able to navigate through live scan data taken on-site at the University. This connection with their local environment allowed them to inspect the data in an area familiar to them and this really helped to bring the 'real-world' connection to the project launch.

To complement the data capture aspect of LiDAR scanning demonstrations, students also had the opportunity to use HTC Vive Pro VR headsets to fly through Google Earth VR. During this demonstration students were awestruck with the level of detail and how real it felt to fly over the earth. This also allowed them to see the full technology process from LiDAR data capture to Google Earth VR output that was created using satellite imagery, LiDAR scans and photogrammetry.

3 FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The planning and implementation of this pilot module was both exciting and challenging. One of the core values at the University is that 'we relish challenge and reach for the previously unachievable' [16]. Designing and implementing new teaching and learning methodologies isn't straight forward and it requires disruptive thinking, innovation and resilience.

3.1 Module planning

Challenges encountered during design and planning included timetabling over 200 students into small group activities, finding suitable learning spaces for project-based activities, a lack of trained GSPBL facilitators and a requirement for different methods of multimedia assessment.

The authors are fortunate that the support networks at the University of Exeter are incredibly willing and able to overcome issues and have already developed some solutions. Examples include best practice timetabling strategies from previous experience with the School of Medicine, a list of all learning spaces suitable for PBL with a 360 online view, refurbishment of engineering learning spaces to facilitate project-based activities, GSPBL training for current and new staff and the development of high-quality assessment criteria for multimedia assessments.

3.2 Module delivery

3.2.1 Project Launch

There is no doubt that students were fully engaged during the project launch. It was a brilliant way to start a module and the energy generated on the day with so many industry colleagues on-site with exciting equipment. Watching students interact with the equipment and ask the experts many questions was a testament to this aspect of GSPBL and EntreComp. The key observation was that students were happy, smiling

and laughing and enjoying trying out equipment with their peers and chatting with colleagues from industry in a relaxing, small group experience. Some students were interviewed following the project launch and made the following comments:

'Project Based Learning helps communication with other people from different sections of engineering such as civil, mechanical [and] electrical and so on ... Although it's the first 3 weeks of the course, you can already sense that the group projects are really going to help us collaborate and also learn about LiDAR.'

'By doing stuff like this it really brings it to life, whereas we're in the classroom and in lectures learning about it but when you get to put on the goggles and the VR stuff it like, really opens your eyes to what you can use it for and just, I don't know, it kind of blows your mind a little bit for the potential of what you can do with it, so yeah for me it was amazing.'

'Hands on experience is that link between the theory and the actual application of what you have learnt, so the two combined allows you to have the necessary skills to enter the workforce.'

'[VR can be used] for architecture and design for architects to produce designs and projects and plans and actually be able to communicate those with others.'

'Not only do you get to learn about what other ... engineers do, but you also get to apply what you do in the entrepreneurship, skills and development course and understand what you can potentially do later on.'

'What's so great about the course and the hands-on experience is the fact you get to learn transferrable skills, I think it's very beneficial for like future projects and future employment.'

'I think it's just kind of opened my mind a lot more and kind of made me realise the opportunities and the fact that technology is moving so incredibly quickly and I would quite like to be involved with that because it's very exciting.'

These comments illustrate that the methodology applied to this module helps students to appreciate the benefit of collaboration and building a learning community, authenticity, linking theory with practice, linking entrepreneurship competences with employability and it also inspires students to keep up to date with rapidly advancing technology.

3.2.2 Challenges with building the GSPBL culture

The delivery of this module generated challenges which were documented through accelerate feedback and during a feedback lecture with students. Some students found it challenging to adjust to this new type of teaching and learning after very different national and international experiences at school level. A minority of students found it difficult to form team bonds, were too shy to post on the VLE forum, struggled with the open-ended driving question, blended learning and didn't appreciate the worth of entrepreneurship and multimedia assessment. Some international students found it difficult to manage language and cultural differences in team situations.

Most of these challenges were expected and can largely be solved by putting more emphasis on building the GSPBL culture over time. The module will be modified to

provide more detail in the introductory lecture to convey the challenges they will face during the 4th industrial revolution. The new methodology combining GSPBL and EntreComp will be explained so students understand that the module is structured to facilitate the acquisition of the required entrepreneurial competences, technical skills and multimedia experience. Outdoor team building activities are planned to overcome individual barriers and build team rapport, trust and create stronger team bonds. More small group project support sessions will be timetabled to build confidence and build the GSPBL culture. A stronger link will be created between the formative and summative assessment to develop a portfolio style of collated work to demonstrate progression (*Table 1*).

3.2.3 Achievements

Although challenges were identified in accelerate feedback, the positive comments suggest that students were engaged by new methodology.

'I love ... [that] ... the students [had] free reign on how to approach and go forward with our idea ... the course felt structured such that we had a clear objective in sight ... unstructured in the sense that our path to the objective was our decision.'

'LiDAR [scanners] are really fascinating and can't wait to pursue a career in them.'

'I can't think of anything negative about this course, you could say that I had the time of my life!'

Reflection is one of the GSPBL seven essential project design elements [2] and student teams submitted a reflective report after their final summative assessment. In the EntreComp part of the questionnaire, student teams were asked to 'list the entrepreneurial skills (as shown on the EntreComp wheel) you think you have most improved as a team during this module?' The following pie chart (*Fig. 3*) shows the percentage of each competence selected. These are grouped into the 3 EntreComp areas:

- Ideas & Opportunities (Blue);
- Resources (Orange);
- Into Action (Green).

These initial results from the team reflective reports and observations by academic members of staff during the module suggest that students progressed further than the expected Foundation Level 1 (Discover) and Level 2 (Explore) [3, pg. 20] and the majority (56%) of the self-assessed and observed competences were in the action area associated with Level 3 (Experiment) and Level 4 (Dare). EntreComp state that 'Level 3 focuses on critical thinking and on experimenting with creating value, for instance through practical experiential experiences' ... 'Level 4 focusses on turning ideas into action in 'real life' and on taking responsibility for this' [3, pg. 20].

Fig. 3. Student assessed EntreComp competences gained during the project.

Initial evidence suggests that designing engineering modules to include the GSPBL seven essential project design elements facilitates students gaining competences associated with Level 3 and 4 of the EntreComp Progression Model [3, pg. 20]. Engineering students need to develop a thirst for life-long learning and harness their human potential in preparation for the 4th industrial revolution.

Future work is currently underway to refine the methodology for Entrepreneurship 1, Entrepreneurship 2 and continue to apply this methodology to the design of new engineering degree programmes at the University of Exeter.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A pilot module (Entrepreneurship 1) facilitated action research with a methodology that combined Gold Standard Project Based Learning (GSPBL) [2] and EntreComp [3] as part of strategic curriculum development. The methodology for designing this pilot module followed the ‘5 steps for designing a project’ [13] for GSPBL. The team project started with an industry linked launch day with hands on LiDAR and VR technology demonstrations. The planning, delivery and assessment of the pilot module posed challenges but results from reflective reports and academic observations illustrated that the proposed methodology helped students develop competences in Level 3 and 4 of the EntreComp progression model [3, pg. 20] and empowered them to take risks, make their own choices and take control of their learning journey. The authors plan to refine the methodology and continue to apply it to the design of new engineering degree programmes at the University of Exeter.

The work undertaken to develop this module was a team effort and relied on brilliant support from the academic teaching team, education and student support, technical services and innovation and impact and business at the University of Exeter. Our industry colleagues at Teradata UK Ltd and Hoare Lea LLP played a major part in the success of the project launch day.

REFERENCES

- [1] Desai, M. (2018). Engineering Education and the Fourth Industrial Revolution, unpublished paper submitted to the Government's Education Select Committee.
- [2] PBLWorks. (2019). WHAT: Gold Standard PBL: Essential Project Design Elements. [online] Available at: <https://www.pblworks.org/what-is-pbl/gold-standard-project-design> (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019).
- [3] McCallum, E., Weicht, R., McMullan, L., Price, A. (2018). EntreComp into Action: get inspired, make it happen, M. Bacigalupo & W. O'Keeffe Eds., *EUR 29105 EN*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, pg.14, pg. 15 & pg. 20.
- [4] Osterwalder, A. (2012). The Business Model Canvas. Available at: <https://youtu.be/2FumwkBMhLo> (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019).
- [5] The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA) (2012). Enterprise and entrepreneurship education: Guidance for UK higher education providers Available at: https://supportthere.org/sites/default/files/uk_qaa-entrepreneurship-guidance_2012.pdf (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019). (pp. 24-25).
- [6] The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA) (2018). Enterprise and entrepreneurship education: Guidance for UK higher education providers Available at: https://www.qaa.ac.uk/docs/qaa/about-us/enterprise-and-entrepreneurship-education-2018.pdf?sfvrsn=20e2f581_10 (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019). (pp. 13-16).
- [7] Graham, R. (2018). The Global State of the Art in Engineering Education, MIT School of Engineering.
- [8] Mitchell, J, Nyamapfene, A, Roach, K and Tilley, E. (2019), Faculty wide curriculum reform: the integrated engineering programme, European Journal of Engineering Education.
- [9] Hannon, P. (2018). Is This the End of Universities as We Know Them? in The Future of Universities Thoughtbook, Universities Industry Innovation Network, Amsterdam, pp.23-24.
- [10] Larmer, J, Mergendoller and J, Boss, S (2015). Setting the Standard for Project Based Learning, ASCD, Alexandria, VA, pg. xi-6.
- [11] PBLWorks. (2019). 21st Century Skills Table. Available at: https://my.pblworks.org/system/files/documents/BIE_21stCenturySkills_table_version4.pdf (Accessed 26 Apr. 2019).
- [12] Mergendoller, J. (2018). Defining High Quality PBL: A Look at the Research. Available at: <https://hqpbl.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Defining-High-Quality-PBL-A-Look-at-the-Research-.pdf> (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019).

- [13] Larmer, J. (2018). Getting started with project based learning. 1st ed. Alexandria, VA: ASCD, p.2.
- [14] Engineering Council (2018). Accreditation of Higher Education Programmes (AHEP). Available at: <https://www.engc.org.uk/ahep> (Accessed 24 Apr. 2019).
- [15] Edgett, S. (2019). The Stage-Gate® Model: An Overview Available at: <https://www.stage-gate.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/wp10english.pdf>. (Accessed 27 Apr. 2019).
- [16] University of Exeter, Our Values. Available at: <http://www.exeter.ac.uk/ourvalues/>. (Accessed 27 Apr. 2019).